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FEATURES OF DETERMINING THE FINANCIAL CONDITION OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This work covers the theoretical and practical aspects of determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises. The study analyzes the importance of factors such as seasonality, exchange rate fluctuations, competitive environment and profitability of services in assessing the financial stability of the enterprise. Also, methods for assessing the financial potential of the enterprise based on liquidity, profitability, financial independence and working capital ratios were considered. As a result, practical proposals were developed to stabilize the financial condition and increase the efficiency of tourism enterprises.*

Keywords: *tourism, financial condition, financial stability, liquidity, profitability, investment, tourism enterprise, competitive environment, economic analysis.*

Introduction. Currently, the tourism sector is gaining particular importance as one of the fastest growing sectors of the country's economy. Tourism contributes not only to the growth of national income, but also to the creation of new jobs and the expansion of exports of services. At the same time, the sustainable operation of tourism enterprises directly depends on their financial condition.

The financial condition of a tourism enterprise is one of the most important indicators that reflects the state of financial resources formed as a result of its economic activities, the level of their effective management and the solvency of the enterprise. By ensuring financial stability, the enterprise can sustainably conduct its activities for a long time, attract investments and provide competitive services.

In this regard, an in-depth analysis of the financial condition of tourism enterprises, determining their financial stability and developing effective management decisions is one of the current issues. In particular, factors such as seasonality in the tourism sector, demand variability, and exchange rate fluctuations have a significant impact on the financial results of enterprises.

This topic considers the theoretical foundations, analysis methods and practical significance of determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises. Through this, the goal is to assess the financial capabilities of enterprises operating in the tourism sector and identify ways to improve their efficiency.

Literature review. Many domestic and foreign scientists have conducted research on the issue of determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises. Their scientific work is based on the theory of tourism economics, financial management, and ensuring enterprise sustainability.

First of all, F. Kotler and J. Bowen in their work “Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism” emphasized that the economic stability of tourism enterprises is inextricably linked with the marketing strategy and showed the importance of financial analysis in forming a profitable portfolio of services. In their opinion, the cost structure and service segmentation require special attention when assessing the financial condition.

M.Porter’s concept of “Competitive Advantage” notes that the financial success of tourism enterprises should be based on a competitive strategy and market analysis. He emphasizes the importance of differentiated services and strict control over costs in increasing financial stability.

Uzbek economists A.Vahobov, R.Abdullayev, Sh.Kholiqulov and others studied the issues of increasing the economic efficiency of tourism enterprises and ensuring their financial stability, and developed theoretical and practical recommendations in this direction. In particular, A.Vakhobov in his work “Corporate Finance” emphasizes the importance of analyzing liquidity, profitability and working capital ratios in assessing the financial condition.

Also, in the studies of H.Yuldoshev and M.Saidov on the economics of tourism, the factors of tourism development in our country, the investment environment, infrastructure

and specific aspects of the financial management system were analyzed. In their opinion, the financial condition of tourism enterprises largely depends on external factors - state support, tax breaks and the availability of credit resources.

In foreign practice, R.Briham and J.Houston in their work “Financial Management: Theory and Practice” state that the financial analysis of an enterprise is determined by the balance between assets, liabilities and capital structure. This approach is also suitable for tourism enterprises, since they manage their resources based on seasonal income.

In recent years, due to the expansion of e-tourism and the system of digital services, the studies of D.Buhalis and R.Lawlar deserve special attention. They proved that digital transformation is an important factor in optimizing financial flows and increasing profit margins in the tourism sector. In general, the analysis of the existing literature shows that when determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises, it is necessary not to be limited to the analysis of accounting data alone, but also to comprehensively study market, marketing, investment and organizational factors. This approach allows the enterprise to ensure strategic stability and gain competitive advantage.

Research methodology. In conducting the research, various methods and models, analytical tools were effectively used to highlight the features of determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises.

Analysis and results. Determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises is the process of assessing the efficiency of using financial resources formed as a result of their activities, their solvency, liquidity level and financial stability. This process is carried out by analyzing the general economic condition of the enterprise, studying its sources of income and the structure of its expenses.

A specific feature of the tourism industry is that this industry is very sensitive to seasonality, external factors (economic, political, environmental) and variability in demand. Therefore, the following features are taken into account when conducting a financial analysis of tourism enterprises:

1. Seasonality factor. Revenues in tourism are not distributed evenly throughout the year. In some months, revenue is high, and in some, it is low. Therefore, when assessing the

financial condition, it is necessary to conduct an analysis in terms of quarters or months, in addition to annual averages.

2. Currency income and expenses. Most tourist services are international in nature and are carried out in foreign currency. Therefore, changes in the exchange rate directly affect the financial stability of the enterprise.

3. Analysis of liquidity and solvency. Tourist enterprises in most cases operate on an advance payment basis, which has a positive effect on the structure of current assets. At the same time, long-term investments and capital turnover are slow.

4. Prices for services and the competitive environment. When assessing the financial condition, the profitability of services, pricing policy, and competitors' offers are also analyzed. Providing low-cost but high-quality services strengthens financial stability.

5. Key financial indicators.

- o Liquidity ratios (current, quick, absolute) - assess the ability of the enterprise to cover short-term obligations.

- o Financial independence ratio - determines the share of own funds.

- o Profitability indicators - show the ratio of net profit to assets, capital or income.

- o Working capital turnover - serves to determine the efficiency of using funds.

6. Dependence on tourism infrastructure. The financial condition of the enterprise largely depends on the level of development of external infrastructure - transport, hotels, service sectors. Therefore, macroeconomic factors are also taken into account in the analysis process.

In conclusion, when determining the financial condition of tourism enterprises, it is necessary not only to study the balance sheet, but also to conduct a comprehensive analysis of factors such as market conditions, seasonality, exchange rate, investment environment and marketing activities. Only then will the real financial potential and development prospects of the enterprise be determined.

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